

The Modular Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes (MHSP)

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Abstract: This study introduces the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice grid (MHL) as a fundamental concept in Number Theory, showcasing its unique property of self-generating under rotations. The development of the MHL involves the creation of a new function termed the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice function (MHL), which exhibits an isomorphic relationship with the modulo function. By exploring the periodicity of number sequences within the MHL grid, connections between decimal expansions and continued fractions are established, paving the way for future investigations. Furthermore, this study elucidates the Map of Integers and their Divisors (MID), an established concept with historical antecedents, while prompting further investigation into unresolved facets. Additionally, it explores the relationship between points on the MHL grid and parabolas [9]/hyperbolas [8], ultimately revealing the Modular Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes (MHSP) as an innovative method for sieving prime numbers within this framework.

Keywords: Sieve of prime numbers; highly composite numbers; factors; pair of complementary divisors; fundamental theorem of arithmetic.

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In a first formal logic class, the teacher posed the classic question: "Why do we need to study mathematics?" One student glanced at their peers, prompting a brief silence before one responded, "I'm not sure, professor. Why should I study mathematics?" "Son, there is no rich person who doesn't know mathematics. But just because you study mathematics doesn't mean you will be a rich person."

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1 Introduction

This study starts by introducing the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice grid (MHL), a fundamental framework in modular arithmetic distinguished by its exceptional property of self-generation upon rotation. In contrast to the Full Multiplication Table (FMT) [17], where rotations alter polynomial degrees in verticals and diagonals, the equations defining MHL elements remain unchanged during rotations.

The construction of the MHL involves the introduction of the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice function (MHL), showcasing an isomorphic relationship with the modulo function, forming the basis for this lattice grid's generation.

Remarkably, all number sequences within the MHL grid's vertical columns and horizontal rows display identical periodicity, allowing for comparisons among their decimal expansions, factorials, and continued fractions. While the detailed analysis of these connections is deferred for future exploration, their significance remains apparent.

Advancing further, this study elaborates on the Map of Integers and their Divisors (MID), a concept previously explored in mathematical research. Historical references, including works by Ventrella [46], Cox [3], and Pol [37][38], suggest prior investigations dating back potentially to Eratosthenes' era. However, due to the absence of documented or lost historical records, a comprehensive understanding of these antecedents might have eluded research efforts.

This study sets the stage for future inquiries to delve deeper into unexplored territories within MID, aiming to provide conclusive answers to persisting questions.

Finally, this study concludes by unveiling the correlation between points on the MHL grid and hyperbolas, forming the foundation of the Modular Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes (MHSP), a pioneering method for sieving prime numbers within this modular hyperbolic framework.

2 Constructing the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice Grid

We embark on the construction of the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice (MHL) grid, a geometric structure defined in the first quadrant of the XY plane. This grid is formed row by row, with each row being filled using a periodic sequence, resulting in a distinctive hyperbolic-like pattern. As we progress, it is crucial to note that while our initial construction takes place in the first quadrant, the structure can and will be expanded to encompass the entire XY plane.

2.1 Algorithm

1. Row at $y = 1$:
 - Periodic sequence <https://oeis.org/A000012> Period 1: *repeat[1](Repunit)*
 - MHL Function: $MHL[x, 1] = 1 + ((x - 1) \bmod 1)$

- Isomorphism: <https://oeis.org/A000004> $MOD[x, 1] = x \bmod 1$
2. Row at $y = 2$:
 - Periodic sequence <https://oeis.org/A000034> Period 2: *repeat*[1, 2]
 - MHL Function: $MHL[x, 2] = 1 + ((x - 1) \bmod 2)$
 - Isomorphism: <https://oeis.org/A000035> $MOD[x, 2] = x \bmod 2$
 3. Row at $y = 3$:
 - Periodic sequence <https://oeis.org/A010882> Period 3: *repeat* [1,2,3]
 - MHL Function: $MHL[x, 3] = 1 + ((x - 1) \bmod 3)$
 - Isomorphism: <https://oeis.org/A010872> $MOD[x, 3] = x \bmod 3$
- ... and so forth.

General MHL function:

$$MHL[x, y] = x \text{ mhl } y = 1 + ((x - 1) \bmod y)$$

In this function, an offset (shift) of 1 is applied to the index x of the MOD function, and one unit is added to compensate for the offset. Unlike $(x \bmod y)$, $(x \text{ mhl } y)$ never results in 0.

2.2 Visualization

Referencing Figure 1, each point with integer coordinates in the 1st quadrant of the XY-plane corresponds to a modular value determined by its position in the integer X and Y coordinates. The horizontal counting (Tally) within each row of value y starts at 1, progresses until it reaches the maximum y -value, and then restarts from 1 at the next point, establishing the periodicity crucial for the modular property in the MHL grid.

Figure 1. C000716 The $MHL[x, y] = x \text{ mhl } y = 1 + ((x - 1) \bmod y)$ in the 1st quadrant of the XY plane.

In constructing the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice (MHL) grid, the values assigned to MHL points are determined by the integer coordinates of those points. The following algorithm outlines the computation of the value for each MHL grid point:

- If $x \bmod y \neq 0$, then $MHL[x, y] = x \bmod y$.
- If $x \bmod y = 0$, then $MHL[x, y] = y$.

Figure 2. C000716 The MHL - Modular Hyperbolic Lattice grid and the integer coordinates.

In simpler terms, when the remainder of the division $x \div y$ is not zero, the MHL value for the point (x, y) is $x \bmod y$. Conversely, when the remainder is zero, the MHL value is y .

Let us delve into examples to better grasp the application of this algorithm:

- For the point $(x, y) = (7, 5)$ is $MHL[7,5] = 2$ because $7 \bmod 5 = 2 \neq 0$.
- For the point $(x, y) = (5, 7)$ is $MHL[5,7] = 5$ because $5 \bmod 7 = 5 \neq 0$.
- For the point $(x, y) = (5, 3)$ is $MHL[3,5] = 2$ because $5 \bmod 3 = 2 \neq 0$.
- For the point $(x, y) = (4, 4)$ is $MHL[4,4] = 4$ because $4 \bmod 4 = 0$, and $y = 4$.
- For the point $(x, y) = (6, 3)$ is $MHL[6,3] = 3$ because $6 \bmod 3 = 0$, and $y = 3$.

This algorithm provides a systematic way to derive MHL values based on the relationships between the integer coordinates of the points in the first quadrant of the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice grid.

2.3 Significance and Applications:

The Modular Hyperbolic Lattice (MHL) grid plays a pivotal role in illuminating the intricate relationship between integers and their divisors. By systematically assigning modular values to points within the grid based on integer coordinates, the MHL provides a visual representation of the division and modulus operations.

One of the primary applications of the MHL is in the realm of number theory. Researchers and mathematicians use the grid to gain deeper insights into the distribution of divisors and the patterns that emerge when exploring the divisibility of integers. The hybrid hyperbolic-parabolic structure of the MHL facilitates the study of divisor relationships in a visually intuitive manner.

Moreover, the MHL finds utility in the investigation of number sequences and the behavior of prime numbers. The periodicity inherent in the grid aids in the identification of regularities and anomalies within these sequences, offering a unique perspective on the fundamental properties of integers.

Beyond its applications in number theory, the MHL serves as a valuable educational tool. Its visual representation provides students with a concrete and engaging way to grasp abstract concepts related to integer division and modular arithmetic. The grid becomes a tangible model for exploring mathematical principles and fostering a deeper understanding of number relationships.

3 The Ancient Digital Root

The concept of substituting zero from modular arithmetic with its equivalent non-zero modularity value is not a recent innovation. A comparable process is well-documented in digital root arithmetic, as explored in previous studies (source: [Digital Root](#)). Digital root arithmetic [47] reveals an isomorphism with modular arithmetic when considering modulo 9.

In modulo 9, computations yield results from the set $\{0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8\}$, while digital root arithmetic generates results from the set $\{9,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8\}$. The isomorphism between these two systems is established.

Expanding upon this insight, our present study generalizes the isomorphism to encompass any modular arithmetic. Consider a modular arithmetic function in the form of:

$$MOD[x, y] = x \text{ mod } y$$

In this case, $(mody)$ generates results from the set $\{0,1,2,3, \dots, y - 1\}$, and $(mhl y)$ generates results from the set $\{y, 1,2,3, \dots, y - 1\}$. This fundamental characteristic defines the isomorphism between the MOD and MHL functions.

To align with the notation of the MOD function, we introduce the MHL function notation:

$$MOD[x, y] = x \text{ mod } y$$

$$MHL[x, y] = x \text{ mhl } y$$

The isomorphic function MHL can be expressed in positive and negative forms, defined as follows:

$$MHL[x, (y > 0)] = x \text{ mhl } |y| = 1 + (x - 1 \pmod{|y|})$$

$$MHL[x, (y < 0)] = x \text{ mhl } (-|y|) = -1 + (x + 1 \pmod{-|y|})$$

Alternatively, for any integer y :

$$MHL[x, y] = x \text{ mhl } y = \frac{|y|}{y} + \left(x - \frac{|y|}{y} \pmod{y} \right)$$

In essence, the digital root emerges as a specific case for row $y = 9$:

$$\text{digital root}[x] = dr[x] = MHL[x, 9] = x \text{ mhl } 9 = 1 + (x - 1 \pmod{9})$$

4 The MHL - Modular Hyperbolic Lattice Grid Columns

In Figure 3, we present the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice (MHL) grid in table format, revealing the intricate relationships between integers and their divisors within the 1st quadrant of the XY-plane.

C001432 The MHL[x,y]=x mhl y=1+(x-1 (mod y)) in table format in the 1st quadrant of the XY-plane.

41	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41			
40	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	1			
39	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	1	2			
38	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	1	2	3			
37	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	1	2	3	4			
36	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	1	2	3	4	5			
35	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	1	2	3	4	5	6			
34	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	1	2	3	4	5	6	7			
33	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8			
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28	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13			
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2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23																					

To complement this representation, Figure 4 showcases the isomorphic MOD function in table format, specifically $MOD[x, y] = x \bmod y$, providing a clear visualization of the positions of the divisors for each integer.

C001433 The MOD[x,y]=x mod y in table format in the 1st quadrant of the XY-plane.

41	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	0	
40	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	0	1	
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38	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	0	1	2	3	
37	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	0	1	2	3	4	
36	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	0	1	2	3	4	5	
35	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
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25	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
24	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
23	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
22	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
21	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	
20	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	0	1	
19	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	0	1	2	3	
18	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	0	1	2	3	4	5	
17	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
16	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
15	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
14	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	
13	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	0	1	2	3
12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	0	1	2	3	4	5	
11	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
10	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	
9	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	0	1	2	3	4	5	
8	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	0	1	
7	1	2	3	4	5	6	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	
6	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	2	3	4	5	
5	1	2	3	0	1	2	3	4	0	1	2	3	4	0	1	2	3	4	0	1	2	3	4	0	1	2	3	4	0	1	2	3	4	0	1	2	3	4	0	1		
4	1	2	3	0	1	2	3	0	1	2	3	0	1	2	3	0	1	2	3	0	1	2	3	0	1	2	3	0	1	2	3	0	1	2	3	0	1	2	3	0	1	
3	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	0	1	2	
2	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	

Figure 4. C001433 The $MOD[x, y] = x \bmod y$ in-table format in the 1st quadrant of the XY-plane.

The significance of these tables lies in their ability to unveil the divisors of each integer. Zeroes in a column x result from $x \bmod y = 0$, indicating that the corresponding y values act as divisors of x . For instance, examining column 10 in Figure 4, represented by the sequence <https://oeis.org/A324471> $MOD[10, y] = 10 \bmod y \{0, 0, 1, 2, 0, 4, 3, 2, 1, 0, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, \dots\}$, we observe 4 zeroes, signifying that the positive integer 10 has 4 divisors.

The isomorphic sequence $MHL[10, y] = 10 \bmod y = 1 + (9 \bmod y)$ aligns divisors with the positions of the zeroes in $MOD[10, y]$. This sequence, denoted as [C000017](#), elegantly captures the divisors of 10: 1, 2, 5, and 10.

In summary, the MOD function identifies the places of divisors, while the MHL function provides the corresponding values of those divisors. This nuanced interplay between MOD and

MHL functions offers a rich understanding of the divisors associated with each integer, with OEIS capturing these insights in the sequence <https://oeis.org/A000005>, known as $d(n)$, $\tau(n)$, or $\sigma_0(n)$, representing the number of divisors of n .

The MOD function provides the places of the divisors.
The MHL function provides the values of the divisors.

5 Exploring the Full XY Plane with the MHL

Our exploration expands beyond the first quadrant, extending the MHL sequences to cover all four quadrants of the XY plane.

5.1 The MOD Function in Action

Figures 5 and 6 illustrate the $MOD[x, y] = x \bmod y$ function in the full XY plane for $-20 \leq x, y \leq 20$. The integers or zeros are assigned to the X and Y axes, with two forms of the function displayed in our standard colors.

Figure 5. C001434 The $MOD[x, y] = x \bmod y$ in the full XY plane for $-20 \leq x, y \leq 20$, assigning the integers or zeros to the X and Y axes.

The same two tables above with our standard colors [25]:

Figure 6. C001435 The two forms of the $MOD[x, y] = x \bmod y$ in the full XY plane for $-20 \leq x, y \leq 20$, with our standard colors[25].

5.2 The MHL Function Unveiled

Figures 7 and 8 present the $MHL[x, y] = x \text{ mhl } y = \frac{|y|}{y} + \left(x - \frac{|y|}{y} (\bmod y) \right)$ function in the full XY plane for $-20 \leq x, y \leq 20$. This function shows unique symmetry, handling positive and negative values differently:

$$MHL[x, y > 0] = x \text{ mhl } |y| = 1 + (x - 1 (\bmod |y|))$$

$$MHL[x, y < 0] = x \text{ mhl } (-|y|) = -1 + (x + 1 (\bmod (-|y|)))$$

Figure 7. C001436 The $MHL[x, y] = x \text{ mhl } y = \frac{|y|}{y} + \left(x - \frac{|y|}{y} \pmod{y} \right)$ in the full XY plane for $-20 \leq x, y \leq 20$, assigning the integers or zeros to the X and Y axes.

The same two tables above with our standard colors [25]:

Figure 8. C001437 The $MHL[x, y] = x \text{ mhl } y = \frac{|y|}{y} + \left(x - \frac{|y|}{y} \pmod{y} \right)$ in the full XY plane with the standard colors.

5.3 Sequences Exploring the Sequences of Divisors in Positive Integers

In this section, the vertical columns of the $MHL[x, y]$ represent sequences of divisors for positive integers. A comparative table (Figure 10) correlates $MOD[x, y]$ and $MHL[x, y]$ for values $1 \leq x \leq 20$.

x>0	Equation	Equation in MOD	OEIS / C	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
1	1 mod y	1 mod y.	A057427	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
1	1 mhl y	1+(0 (mod y)).	A000012	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
2	2 mod y	2 mod y.	C000003	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
2	2 mhl y	1+(1 (mod y)).	A040000	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
3	3 mod y	3 mod y.	C000004	0	1	0	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	
3	3 mhl y	1+(2 (mod y)).	C000038	1	1	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	
4	4 mod y	4 mod y.	C000005	0	0	1	0	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	
4	4 mhl y	1+(3 (mod y)).	C000006	1	2	1	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	
5	5 mod y	5 mod y.	C000007	0	1	2	1	0	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	
5	5 mhl y	1+(4 (mod y)).	C000008	1	1	2	1	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	
6	6 mod y	6 mod y.	C000009	0	0	0	2	1	0	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	
6	6 mhl y	1+(5 (mod y)).	C000010	1	2	3	2	1	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	
7	7 mod y	7 mod y.	C000011	0	1	1	3	2	1	0	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	
7	7 mhl y	1+(6 (mod y)).	C000012	1	1	1	3	2	1	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	
8	8 mod y	8 mod y.	C000013	0	0	2	0	3	2	1	0	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	
8	8 mhl y	1+(7 (mod y)).	C000014	1	2	2	4	3	2	1	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	
9	9 mod y	9 mod y.	C000015	0	1	0	1	4	3	2	1	0	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	
9	9 mhl y	1+(8 (mod y)).	C000016	1	1	3	1	4	3	2	1	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	
10	10 mod y	10 mod y.	A324471	0	0	1	2	0	4	3	2	1	0	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	
10	10 mhl y	1+(9 (mod y)).	C000017	1	2	1	2	5	4	3	2	1	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	
11	11 mod y	11 mod y.	C000018	0	1	2	3	1	5	4	3	2	1	0	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	
11	11 mhl y	1+(10 (mod y)).	C000019	1	1	2	3	1	5	4	3	2	1	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	
12	12 mod y	12 mod y.	C000020	0	0	0	0	2	0	5	4	3	2	1	0	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	
12	12 mhl y	1+(11 (mod y)).	C000021	1	2	3	4	2	6	5	4	3	2	1	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	
13	13 mod y	13 mod y.	C000022	0	1	1	1	3	1	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	
13	13 mhl y	1+(12 (mod y)).	C000023	1	1	1	1	3	1	6	5	4	3	2	1	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	13	
14	14 mod y	14 mod y.	C000024	0	0	2	2	4	2	0	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	
14	14 mhl y	1+(13 (mod y)).	C000025	1	2	2	2	4	2	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	14	
15	15 mod y	15 mod y.	C000026	0	1	0	3	0	3	1	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	
15	15 mhl y	1+(14 (mod y)).	C000027	1	1	3	3	5	3	1	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	
16	16 mod y	16 mod y.	C000028	0	0	1	0	1	4	2	0	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	
16	16 mhl y	1+(15 (mod y)).	C000029	1	2	1	4	1	4	2	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16	
17	17 mod y	17 mod y.	C000030	0	1	2	1	2	5	3	1	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	
17	17 mhl y	1+(16 (mod y)).	C000031	1	1	2	1	2	5	3	1	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	17	
18	18 mod y	18 mod y.	C000032	0	0	0	2	3	0	4	2	0	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	
18	18 mhl y	1+(17 (mod y)).	C000033	1	2	3	2	3	6	4	2	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18	
19	19 mod y	19 mod y.	C000034	0	1	1	3	4	1	5	3	1	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	
19	19 mhl y	1+(18 (mod y)).	C000035	1	1	1	3	4	1	5	3	1	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19	
20	20 mod y	20 mod y.	C000036	0	0	2	0	0	2	6	4	2	0	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	
20	20 mhl y	1+(19 (mod y)).	C000037	1	2	2	4	5	2	6	4	2	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	

Figure 9. [C000716](#) Isomorphism between $x \bmod y$ and $x \text{ mhl } y$. Sequences of the divisors for $1 \leq x \leq 20$.

See the correspondent table:

x>0	Formula	Formula in MOD	OEIS / C	OEIS / SNYPO
1	1 mod y	1 mod y	A057427	https://oeis.org/A057427
1	1 mhl y	1+(0 (mod y))	A000012	https://oeis.org/A000012
2	2 mod y	2 mod y	C000003	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887024938141084/
2	2 mhl y	1+(1 (mod y))	A040000	https://oeis.org/A040000
3	3 mod y	3 mod y	C000004	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887026621474249/
3	3 mhl y	1+(2 (mod y))	C000038	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888436044666640/
4	4 mod y	4 mod y	C000005	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887028728140705/
4	4 mhl y	1+(3 (mod y))	C000006	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887030311473880/
5	5 mod y	5 mod y	C000007	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887032858140292/
5	5 mhl y	1+(4 (mod y))	C000008	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887033034806941/
6	6 mod y	6 mod y	C000009	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887035464806698/
6	6 mhl y	1+(5 (mod y))	C000010	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887035624806682/
7	7 mod y	7 mod y	C000011	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887038374806407/
7	7 mhl y	1+(6 (mod y))	C000012	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887038461473065/
8	8 mod y	8 mod y	C000013	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887129074797337/
8	8 mhl y	1+(7 (mod y))	C000014	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887129324797312/
9	9 mod y	9 mod y	C000015	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887131664797078/

9	9 mhl y	1+(8 (mod y))	C000016	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887132438130334/
10	10 mod y	10 mod y	A324471	https://oeis.org/A324471
10	10 mhl y	1+(9 (mod y))	C000017	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1887134508130127/
11	11 mod y	11 mod y	C000018	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888123474697897/
11	11 mhl y	1+(10 (mod y))	C000019	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888123461364565/
12	12 mod y	12 mod y	C000020	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888127698030808/
12	12 mhl y	1+(11 (mod y))	C000021	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888127678030810/
13	13 mod y	13 mod y	C000022	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888128711364040/
13	13 mhl y	1+(12 (mod y))	C000023	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888128891364022/
14	14 mod y	14 mod y	C000024	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888163474693897/
14	14 mhl y	1+(13 (mod y))	C000025	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888163704693874/
15	15 mod y	15 mod y	C000026	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888164998027078/
15	15 mhl y	1+(14 (mod y))	C000027	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888165044693740/
16	16 mod y	16 mod y	C000028	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888166548026923/
16	16 mhl y	1+(15 (mod y))	C000029	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888166648026913/
17	17 mod y	17 mod y	C000030	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888168858026692/
17	17 mhl y	1+(16 (mod y))	C000031	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888168961360015/
18	18 mod y	18 mod y	C000032	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888170304693214/
18	18 mhl y	1+(17 (mod y))	C000033	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888170294693215/
19	19 mod y	19 mod y	C000034	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888182348025343/
19	19 mhl y	1+(18 (mod y))	C000035	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888182448025333/
20	20 mod y	20 mod y	C000036	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888184611358450/
20	20 mhl y	1+(19 (mod y))	C000037	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888184744691770/

Figure 10. [C000716](#) Isomorphism between $x \bmod y$ and $x \text{ mhl } y$. Sequences of the divisors for $1 \leq x \leq 20$.

5.4 Sequences Exploring the Sequences of Divisors in Negative Integers

In this section, the vertical columns of the $MHL[x, y]$ represent sequences of divisors for negative integers. A comparative table (Figure 12) correlates $MOD[x, y]$ and $MHL[x, y]$ for values $-20 \leq x \leq -1$.

x<0	Equation	Equation in MOD	OEIS / C	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30
-1	-1 mod y	-1 mod y.	A001477	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
-1	-1 mhl y	1+(-2 (mod y)).	A028310	1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29
-2	-2 mod y	-2 mod y.	A099570	0	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
-2	-2 mhl y	1+(-3 (mod y)).	C000039	1	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28
-3	-3 mod y	-3 mod y.	A097141	0	1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27
-3	-3 mhl y	1+(-4 (mod y)).	C000040	1	1	3	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27
-4	-4 mod y	-4 mod y.	C000041	0	0	2	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
-4	-4 mhl y	1+(-5 (mod y)).	C000042	1	2	2	4	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26
-5	-5 mod y	-5 mod y.	C000043	0	1	1	3	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25
-5	-5 mhl y	1+(-6 (mod y)).	C000044	1	1	1	3	5	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25
-6	-6 mod y	-6 mod y.	C000045	0	0	0	2	4	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
-6	-6 mhl y	1+(-7 (mod y)).	C000046	1	2	3	2	4	6	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
-7	-7 mod y	-7 mod y.	C000047	0	1	2	1	3	5	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
-7	-7 mhl y	1+(-8 (mod y)).	C000048	1	1	2	1	3	5	7	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23
-8	-8 mod y	-8 mod y.	C000049	0	0	1	0	2	4	6	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
-8	-8 mhl y	1+(-9 (mod y)).	C000050	1	2	1	4	2	4	6	8	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22
-9	-9 mod y	-9 mod y.	C000051	0	1	0	3	1	3	5	7	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
-9	-9 mhl y	1+(-10 (mod y)).	C000052	1	1	3	3	1	3	5	7	9	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
-10	-10 mod y	-10 mod y.	C000053	0	0	2	2	0	2	4	6	8	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
-10	-10 mhl y	1+(-11 (mod y)).	C000054	1	2	2	2	5	2	4	6	8	10	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
-11	-11 mod y	-11 mod y.	C000055	0	1	1	1	4	1	3	5	7	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
-11	-11 mhl y	1+(-12 (mod y)).	C000056	1	1	1	1	4	1	3	5	7	9	11	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
-12	-12 mod y	-12 mod y.	C000057	0	0	0	0	3	0	2	4	6	8	10	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
-12	-12 mhl y	1+(-13 (mod y)).	C000058	1	2	3	4	3	6	2	4	6	8	10	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
-13	-13 mod y	-13 mod y.	C000059	0	1	2	3	2	5	1	3	5	7	9	11	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
-13	-13 mhl y	1+(-14 (mod y)).	C000060	1	1	2	3	2	5	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17
-14	-14 mod y	-14 mod y.	C000061	0	0	1	2	1	4	0	2	4	6	8	10	12	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
-14	-14 mhl y	1+(-15 (mod y)).	C000062	1	2	1	2	1	4	7	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
-15	-15 mod y	-15 mod y.	C000063	0	1	0	1	0	3	6	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
-15	-15 mhl y	1+(-16 (mod y)).	C000064	1	1	3	1	5	3	6	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
-16	-16 mod y	-16 mod y.	C000065	0	0	2	0	4	2	5	0	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
-16	-16 mhl y	1+(-17 (mod y)).	C000066	1	2	2	4	4	2	5	8	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
-17	-17 mod y	-17 mod y.	C000067	0	1	1	3	3	1	4	7	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
-17	-17 mhl y	1+(-18 (mod y)).	C000068	1	1	1	3	3	1	4	7	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
-18	-18 mod y	-18 mod y.	C000069	0	0	0	2	2	0	3	6	0	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
-18	-18 mhl y	1+(-19 (mod y)).	C000070	1	2	3	2	2	6	3	6	9	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
-19	-19 mod y	-19 mod y.	C000071	0	1	2	1	1	5	2	5	8	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
-19	-19 mhl y	1+(-20 (mod y)).	C000072	1	1	2	1	1	5	2	5	8	1	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
-20	-20 mod y	-20 mod y.	C000073	0	0	1	0	0	4	1	4	7	0	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
-20	-20 mhl y	1+(-21 (mod y)).	C000074	1	2	1	4	5	4	1	4	7	10	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18	20	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

Figure 11. [C000716](#) Isomorphism between $x \bmod y$ and $x \text{ mhl } y$. Sequences of the divisors for $-20 \leq x \leq -1$.

See the correspondent table:

x<0	Formula	Formula in MOD	OEIS / C	OEIS / SNYPO
-1	-1 mod y	-1 mod y	A001477	https://oeis.org/A001477
-1	-1 mhl y	1+(-2 (mod y))	A028310	https://oeis.org/A028310
-2	-2 mod y	-2 mod y	A099570	https://oeis.org/A099570
-2	-2 mhl y	1+(-3 (mod y))	C000039	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/18885755462689/
-3	-3 mod y	-3 mod y	A097141	https://oeis.org/A097141
-3	-3 mhl y	1+(-4 (mod y))	C000040	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888576837985894/
-4	-4 mod y	-4 mod y	C000041	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888681027975475/
-4	-4 mhl y	1+(-5 (mod y))	C000042	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888681224642122/
-5	-5 mod y	-5 mod y	C000043	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888682521308659/
-5	-5 mhl y	1+(-6 (mod y))	C000044	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888682634641981/
-6	-6 mod y	-6 mod y	C000045	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888683701308541/
-6	-6 mhl y	1+(-7 (mod y))	C000046	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888683801308531/
-7	-7 mod y	-7 mod y	C000047	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888685971308314/
-7	-7 mhl y	1+(-8 (mod y))	C000048	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888686041308307/
-8	-8 mod y	-8 mod y	C000049	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888687017974876/
-8	-8 mhl y	1+(-9 (mod y))	C000050	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888687087974869/
-9	-9 mod y	-9 mod y	C000051	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888692667974311/

-9	-9 mhl y	1+(-10 (mod y))	C000052	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888692714640973/
-10	-10 mod y	-10 mod y	C000053	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888694034640841/
-10	-10 mhl y	1+(-11 (mod y))	C000054	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888694277974150/
-11	-11 mod y	-11 mod y	C000055	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888695497974028/
-11	-11 mhl y	1+(-12 (mod y))	C000056	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888695581307353/
-12	-12 mod y	-12 mod y	C000057	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888696431307268/
-12	-12 mhl y	1+(-13 (mod y))	C000058	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888696527973925/
-13	-13 mod y	-13 mod y	C000059	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888697781307133/
-13	-13 mhl y	1+(-14 (mod y))	C000060	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888697834640461/
-14	-14 mod y	-14 mod y	C000061	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888700764640168/
-14	-14 mhl y	1+(-15 (mod y))	C000062	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888700864640158/
-15	-15 mod y	-15 mod y	C000063	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888703241306587/
-15	-15 mhl y	1+(-16 (mod y))	C000064	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888703321306579/
-16	-16 mod y	-16 mod y	C000065	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888704991306412/
-16	-16 mhl y	1+(-17 (mod y))	C000066	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888705104639734/
-17	-17 mod y	-17 mod y	C000067	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888707884639456/
-17	-17 mhl y	1+(-18 (mod y))	C000068	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888736391303272/
-18	-18 mod y	-18 mod y	C000069	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888737891303122/
-18	-18 mhl y	1+(-19 (mod y))	C000070	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888737944636450/
-19	-19 mod y	-19 mod y	C000071	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888738827969695/
-19	-19 mhl y	1+(-20 (mod y))	C000072	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888738877969690/
-20	-20 mod y	-20 mod y	C000073	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888739771302934/
-20	-20 mhl y	1+(-21 (mod y))	C000074	https://www.facebook.com/groups/snypo/posts/1888739814636263/

Figure 12. [C000716](#) Isomorphism between $x \bmod y$ and $x \text{ mhl } y$. Sequences of the divisors for $-20 \leq x \leq -1$.

This comprehensive exploration of divisors in both positive and negative integers using the MHL grid offers a visual representation and paves the way for intriguing findings when examining decimal expansions, continued fractions, and more.

Decimal expansion	Decimal expansion of	Continued Fraction	Equation
0.0^{-1}	1/90	[0; 90]	1 mod y
$0.^{-1}$	1/9	[0; 9]	1 mhl y
0.00^{-2}	1/450	[0; 450]	2 mod y
0.1^{-2}	11/90	[0; 8, 5, 2]	2 mhl y
0.010^{-3}	31/3000	[0; 96, 1, 3, 2, 3]	3 mod y
0.11^{-3}	17/150	[0; 8, 1, 4, 1, 2]	3 mhl y
0.0010^{-4}	47/45000	[0; 957, 2, 4, 5]	4 mod y
0.121^{-4}	1093/9000	[0; 8, 4, 3, 1, 2, 2, 4, 2]	4 mhl y
0.01210^{-5}	2179/180000	[0; 82, 1, 1, 1, 1, 5, 2, 1, 2, 2, 1, 2]	5 mod y
0.1121^{-5}	5047/45000	[0; 8, 1, 10, 1, 13, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2]	5 mhl y
0.000210^{-6}	79/375000	[0; 4746, 1, 5, 13]	6 mod y
0.12321^{-6}	7393/60000	[0; 8, 8, 1, 1, 1, 3, 25, 1, 2]	6 mhl y
0.0113210^{-7}	1018897/90000000	[0; 88, 3, 43, 1, 2, 1, 15, 2, 3, 2, 7]	7 mod y
0.111321^{-7}	125237/1125000	[0; 8, 1, 57, 1, 2, 2, 75, 1, 3]	7 mhl y
0.00203210^{-8}	914449/450000000	[0; 492, 10, 25, 1, 4, 3, 43, 1, 4]	8 mod y
0.1224321^{-8}	11018897/900000000	[0; 8, 5, 1, 23, 1, 30, 2, 61, 2, 1, 2, 2]	8 mhl y
0.010143210^{-9}	10143211/1000000000	[0; 98, 1, 1, 2, 2, 1, 26, 1, 6, 1, 3, 3, 12, 3, 2, 2]	9 mod y
0.11314321^{-9}	5657161/500000000	[0; 8, 1, 5, 5, 2, 1, 2, 1, 10, 2, 4, 1, 10, 1, 1, 1, 3]	9 mhl y
0.00120432^{-10}	5961389/4950000000	[0; 830, 2, 1, 10, 2, 1, 2, 6, 1, 3050]	10 mod y
0.121254321^{-10}	1200417778/999000000000	[0; 832, 4, 1, 3, 10, 2, 3, 2, 1, 15, 1, 18, 1, 7, 3, 1, 11]	10 mhl y

Figure 13. [C000716](#) The continued fraction and decimal expansion of $x \bmod y$, and $x \text{ mhl } y$.

6 Introducing the MID - A Comprehensive Map of Integers and Their Divisors

By focusing solely on the periods of rows determined by the periodic sequences $MHL[x, y] = x \text{ mhl } y = 1 + ((x - 1) \bmod y)$, we can generate a unique figure in the XY plane.

Figure 14. The Map of the Integers and their Divisors (MID). Integer numbers are in the X-axis coordinates and their divisors are in the Y-axis coordinates.

Figure 14 represents this concept, which we will refer to as the Map of the Integers and their Divisors, or MID for short. In this map, integer numbers are represented along the X-axis, while their corresponding divisors are plotted along the Y-axis.

The MID is divided into four quadrants, each with Y-coordinates representing the divisors of the corresponding X-coordinate. For instance, in the verticals $x = \pm 6$, points exist only at the coordinates $y \in (\pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \pm 6)$, all of which are divisors of the integer ± 6 .

For the sake of clarity and aesthetics, we will consistently omit the infinite integer divisors of zero that are distributed along the entire Y-axis.

This innovative approach provides a visual exploration of integers and their divisors, offering a deeper understanding of their relationships and properties.

7 Exploring the Linear Patterns of Divisors in the MID

In the MID, it is possible to draw an infinite number of lines of the form $x = (b^{\pm 1})y$, each separating distinct integer modularities. Each line contains a sequence of integers, with the integers on the blue lines linearly distributed as divisors of all integers on the X-axis.

Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference.: Unraveling the Periodicity in the MHL Grid

Figure 15. C000717 showcases the red and blue lines of all MID divisors in the form $x = (b^{\pm 1})y$, revealing the periodicity inherent in the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice (MHL) grid. The blue lines demonstrate the periodicity in the horizontal rows, while the red lines exhibit the periodicity in the vertical columns.

We have stylized most of the points with an unfilled circle, representing points that are not divisors of their X or Y coordinates. In contrast, all filled points are divisors of either X or Y coordinates.

The red lines, represented by $x = b^{-1}y$ where $b > 0$, encompass all divisors of the integer coordinates of the Y-axis. Similarly, the blue lines, represented by $x = by$ where $b > 0$, cover all divisors of the integer coordinates of the X-axis.

We have highlighted the $45^\circ x = y$ diagonal line in yellow as it represents points that are the greatest divisor of their equal integer coordinates, embodying both "blue and red" types simultaneously.

Each line covers all positive integers, which are the divisors of either the X, Y, or both X and Y coordinates. These lines are henceforth referred to as the lines of the MID divisors.

8 Unveiling the Geometric Patterns of MID Divisors through Triangles

In the realm of the MID, we can construct an infinite array of lines in the form $x=by$, each encapsulating the entire modularity of the X-axis. This intriguing phenomenon is depicted below:

Figure 16. C000718: The Infinite Array of Triangles Formed by Divisor Lines

These lines give rise to an infinite series of triangles, each possessing identical elements arranged in the same sequence. Interestingly, a bijection exists between all elements residing within these triangles.

Sequences sharing the same color are identical. Despite the presence of infinite identical rotations, the modular lattice structure ensures no offset between the sequences.

The red lines represent the infinite Repunit (refer to OEIS sequence <https://oeis.org/A000012>) with the equation $Y[y] = 0 \text{ mhl } y = 1 + (0 \pmod{y})$. The green lines correspond to the sequence found in OEIS <https://oeis.org/A040000>, represented by the equation $Y[y] = 2 \text{ mhl } y = 1 + (1 \pmod{y})$. The blue lines almost represent the sequence in OEIS <https://oeis.org/A290858> or exactly match the sequence found in this [Facebook post](#), with the equation $Y[y] = 3 \text{ mhl } y = 1 + (2 \pmod{y})$. The pattern continues in a similar fashion.

The black lines symbolize the positive integers (refer to OEIS sequence <https://oeis.org/A000027>) with the equation $Y[y] = y$. The first black line in the 1st quadrant corresponds to the Y-axis.

This exploration unveils the intricate geometric patterns formed by the divisors in the MID, offering a deeper understanding of their inherent relationships.

9 Exploring Rotations in the MHL Framework

Like the FMT [17], the MHL framework allows for the implementation of rotations. Due to its inherent modularity, all rotations, whether clockwise or counterclockwise, yield identical structures. This characteristic imparts a fractal-like nature to the MHL, as all values are modular or cyclic.

9.1 Fractions that generate the recurring in rows Y

An intriguing aspect of the MHL is the ability to compare the simplest fractions that generate equivalent recurring sequences with three specific denominators: Repunit, “Repthree”, and “Repnine”. Fractions that fail to generate these sequences are highlighted with a reddish background, providing a visual cue for further investigation.

OEIS	$1 + (x \bmod y)$	Recurring using Repeat[9]	Recurring using Repeat[3]	Recurring using Repunit
A000012	$1 + (x \bmod 1)$	$\frac{1}{9} = \frac{0.\overline{3}}{3} = \frac{0.\overline{1}}{1} = 0.\overline{1}$	$\frac{4}{3} = 1.\overline{3}$	$\frac{1}{1} = 1.\overline{0}$
A000034	$1 + (x \bmod 2)$	$\frac{12}{99} = 0.\overline{12}$	$\frac{4}{33} = 0.\overline{12}$	$\frac{1}{11} = 0.\overline{09}$
A010882	$1 + (x \bmod 3)$	$\frac{123}{999} = 0.\overline{123}$	$\frac{41}{333} = 0.\overline{123}$	$\frac{13}{111} = 0.\overline{117}$
A010883	$1 + (x \bmod 4)$	$\frac{1234}{9999} = 0.\overline{1234}$	$\frac{411}{3333} = 0.\overline{1233}$	$\frac{137}{1111} = 0.\overline{1233}$
A010884	$1 + (x \bmod 5)$	$\frac{12345}{99999} = 0.\overline{12345}$	$\frac{4115}{33333} = 0.\overline{12345}$	$\frac{1371}{11111} = 0.\overline{12339}$
A010885	$1 + (x \bmod 6)$	$\frac{123456}{999999} = 0.\overline{123456}$	$\frac{41152}{333333} = 0.\overline{123456}$	$\frac{13717}{111111} = 0.\overline{123453}$
A010886	$1 + (x \bmod 7)$	$\frac{1234567}{9999999} = 0.\overline{1234567}$	$\frac{411522}{3333333} = 0.\overline{1235466}$	$\frac{137174}{1111111} = 0.\overline{1235466}$
A010887	$1 + (x \bmod 8)$	$\frac{12345678}{99999999} = 0.\overline{12345678}$	$\frac{4115226}{33333333} = 0.\overline{12345678}$	$\frac{1371742}{11111111} = 0.\overline{12345678}$
A177274	$1 + (x \bmod 9)$	$\frac{123456789}{999999999} = 0.\overline{123456789}$	$\frac{41152263}{333333333} = 0.\overline{123456789}$	$\frac{13717421}{111111111} = 0.\overline{123456789}$
A010889	$1 + (x \bmod 10)$	$\frac{12345678910}{9999999999} = 0.\overline{12345678910}$	$\frac{4115226303}{3333333333} = 0.\overline{12345678909}$	$\frac{1371742101}{11111111111} = 0.\overline{12345678909}$

Figure 17. Fractions that generate the recurring equivalent to the form of $1 + (x \bmod y)$.

OEIS	$x \bmod y$	Divisions by Repeat[9]	Divisions by Repeat[3]	Divisions by Repunit
A000004	$x \bmod 1$	$\frac{0}{9} = 0.\overline{0}$	$\frac{0.\overline{0}}{3} = 0.\overline{0}$	$\frac{0.\overline{0}}{1} = 0.\overline{0}$
A000035	$x \bmod 2$	$\frac{1}{99} = 0.\overline{01}$	$\frac{0.\overline{3}}{33} = 0.\overline{01}$	$\frac{0.\overline{1}}{11} = 0.\overline{01}$
A010872	$x \bmod 3$	$\frac{12}{999} = 0.\overline{012}$	$\frac{4}{333} = 0.\overline{012}$	$\frac{1}{111} = 0.\overline{009}$; $\frac{2}{111} = 0.\overline{018}$
A010873	$x \bmod 4$	$\frac{123}{9999} = 0.\overline{0123}$	$\frac{41}{3333} = 0.\overline{0123}$	$\frac{13}{1111} = 0.\overline{0117}$; $\frac{14}{1111} = 0.\overline{0126}$
A010874	$x \bmod 5$	$\frac{1234}{99999} = 0.\overline{01234}$	$\frac{411}{33333} = 0.\overline{01233}$	$\frac{137}{11111} = 0.\overline{01233}$
A010875	$x \bmod 6$	$\frac{12345}{999999} = 0.\overline{012345}$	$\frac{4115}{333333} = 0.\overline{012345}$	$\frac{1371}{111111} = 0.\overline{012339}$
A010876	$x \bmod 7$	$\frac{123456}{9999999} = 0.\overline{0123456}$	$\frac{41152}{3333333} = 0.\overline{0123456}$	$\frac{13717}{1111111} = 0.\overline{0123453}$
A010877	$x \bmod 8$	$\frac{1234567}{99999999} = 0.\overline{01234567}$	$\frac{411522}{33333333} = 0.\overline{01234566}$	$\frac{137174}{11111111} = 0.\overline{01234566}$
A010878	$x \bmod 9$	$\frac{12345678}{999999999} = 0.\overline{012345678}$	$\frac{4115226}{333333333} = 0.\overline{012345678}$	$\frac{1371742}{111111111} = 0.\overline{012345678}$
A010879	$x \bmod 10$	$\frac{123456789}{9999999999} = 0.\overline{0123456789}$	$\frac{41152263}{3333333333} = 0.\overline{0123456789}$	$\frac{13717421}{1111111111} = 0.\overline{0123456789}$

Figure 18. Fractions that generate the recurring equivalent to the form of $(x \bmod y)$.

10 The MHL Sieve of Primes

The MHL is a lattice of points in the form of modular arithmetic, where each point has the coordinates (x, y) and the value $x \bmod y$. Modular arithmetic involves only division, and the numerator and denominator are the integers of the X and Y axes. Therefore, we can use the equation $xy = n^2$ to generate hyperbolas that pass through the points of the MHL. We can write this equation in modular form as:

$$H(x, y) = xy = n^2 = \text{square}$$

$$MHL(x, y) = x \bmod y$$

We have match at:

$$x \bmod y = xy \bmod y = n^2 \bmod y = \text{square mod } y$$

Figure 19. C000719 The MHL - Modular Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes.

The line $x = y$ is an axis of symmetry that divides the first quadrant into two octants. We mark the points that are crossed by hyperbolas with a pink X. In the first octant, the hyperbolas cross the points that satisfy $xy = n^2$, which are on the lines $x = k^2y$. In the second octant, the hyperbolas cross the points that also satisfy $xy = n^2$, which are on the lines $y = k^{-2}x$.

The points with integers on the diagonal line $x = y$ are crossed by hyperbolas of the form $xy = n^2$, where n is an integer. Each point on the hyperbola represents a divisor of n . This is because hyperbola has a constant value of xy . If x is an integer, then $y = \frac{n^2}{x}$ is an integer divisor of n^2 , and vice versa.

Using the integers on the diagonal line $x = y$, we can apply the following sieve to find the prime numbers:

All prime numbers are those whose hyperbolas $xy = n^2$ cross at most three points: one on the diagonal line $x = y = n$, one on the horizontal line $y = 1$ where $x = n^2$, and one on the vertical line $x = 1$ where $y = n^2$. Under this condition, we can consider number 1 a prime number.

All composite numbers are those whose hyperbolas $xy = n^2$ cross at least one point in each octant that is not on the lines $y = 1$ or $x = 1$. Composite numbers are those whose hyperbolas cross an odd number of points greater than three. Because of the symmetry of the two octants, the number of points will always be odd. Under this condition, we can consider number 0 a composite number.

11 The MID Sieve of Primes

When we plot the hyperbolas $xy = n^2$ over the MID, we obtain the following figure:

Figure 20. The $MHL[x, y] = x \text{ mhl } y = 1 + ((x - 1) \bmod y)$ with hyperbolas $xy = n^2$ in the XY plane. This is the Modular Hyperbolic Sieve of Primes (MHSP).

In this case, the sieve operates following the same mechanism that we derived from the sieve in TMT – Triangular Multiplication Table (TMTSP) [17]. For each quadrant:

Composite numbers are those that have hyperbolas covering more than two points in the Map of the Integers and their Divisors (MID). That is, they are the integers that have more than two positive divisors.

Prime numbers are those that have hyperbolas covering one or at most two points in the Map of the Integers and their Divisors (MID). That is, they are the integers that have one or at most two positive divisors.

Here are some examples where we are considering the integers on the X-axis:

- The hyperbola $xy = 0^2 = 0$ intersects the infinitely many points $(x, 0)$, because the integer 0 has infinitely many divisors $0 = \frac{0}{x}$.
- The hyperbola $xy = 1^2 = 1$ intersects only the point $(1, 1)$, because the integer 1 has only divisor $1 = \frac{1}{1}$.
- The hyperbola $xy = 2^2 = 4$ intersects the points $(2, 2)$ and $(1, 4)$, because the integer 2 has two divisors: $2 = \frac{4}{2}$ and $1 = \frac{4}{4}$. All prime numbers have two divisors.
- The hyperbola $xy = 3^2 = 9$ intersects the points $(3, 3)$ and $(1, 9)$, because the integer 3 has two divisors: $3 = \frac{9}{3}$ and $1 = \frac{9}{9}$.
- The hyperbola $xy = 4^2 = 16$ intersects the points $(4, 4)$, $(2, 8)$, and $(1, 16)$, because the integer 4 has three divisors: $4 = \frac{16}{4}$, $2 = \frac{16}{8}$ and $1 = \frac{16}{16}$.
- The hyperbola $xy = 5^2 = 25$ intersects the points $(5, 5)$ and $(1, 25)$, because the integer 5 has two divisors: $5 = \frac{25}{5}$ and $1 = \frac{25}{25}$.
- The hyperbola $xy = 6^2 = 36$ intersects the points $(6, 6)$, $(3, 12)$, $(2, 18)$ and $(1, 36)$, because the integer 6 has four divisors: $6 = \frac{36}{6}$, $3 = \frac{36}{12}$, $2 = \frac{36}{18}$ and $1 = \frac{36}{36}$.
- The hyperbola $xy = 7^2 = 49$ intersects the points $(7, 7)$ and $(1, 49)$, because the integer 7 has two divisors: $7 = \frac{49}{7}$ and $1 = \frac{49}{49}$.
- The hyperbola $xy = 8^2 = 64$ intersects the points $(8, 8)$, $(4, 16)$, $(2, 32)$ and $(1, 64)$, because the integer 8 has four divisors: $8 = \frac{64}{8}$, $4 = \frac{64}{16}$, $2 = \frac{64}{32}$ and $1 = \frac{64}{64}$.
- The hyperbola $xy = 9^2 = 81$ intersects the points $(9, 9)$, $(3, 27)$, and $(1, 81)$, because the integer 9 has three divisors: $9 = \frac{81}{9}$, $3 = \frac{81}{27}$ and $1 = \frac{81}{81}$.
- And so on.

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